

INNOVATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article clarifies about the types of innovative technologies for learning a foreign language and the methods of using them in the classroom, as well as the importance of effective use of methods. Also, special information is given about the fact that these methods will help the students to learn a foreign language thoroughly and be able to speak that language easily.

Key words: education, technology, foreign language, teaching, types of learning.

Today, many fields of modern activity, in particular, the field of education, are developing rapidly due to various innovations. The change in demand in the field of education has led to many changes, which put high demands on the labor force and created the need to improve the training of a sufficient number of qualified workers. We believe that the formation of foreign language competence, which is the main goal of education, is the main goal of today. When it comes to the improvement of twenty-first-century's high-tech, modern technologies make it possible to solve a number of pedagogical problems positively, increases educational activity and develops the culture of independent work of students.

The main superiorities of using innovative technologies in teaching a foreign language instead of traditional methods of information transmission, it is more successful to emphasize training methods through modern gadgets. For learning through improved technologies, we can get a lot of materials, including touch screens, podcasts in order to learning a foreign language we can get speakers to the lesson, and it shows the bright effect on the psychology of young learners.

Technology has become an integral part of teaching and learning of students. It allows them to develop their critical thinking skills, learn new concepts and express their ideas creatively. Technology also allows teachers to accommodate the three main learning styles: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. After identifying these three categories of students well, the teacher guides them to the right path, it will have a good effect on the future of the student while learning foreign languages.

Visual Learning. Visual learning students learn best by reading directions or seeing a demonstration. They often need to see concepts and facts through pictures, diagrams and charts. Teachers can create a PowerPoint that describes key points and includes pictures or specific facts. This simple practice helps to visual learners.

Auditory Learning. Auditory learning students comprehend and remember information through listening and speaking. Presentations and public speaking assignments accommodate this learning style. However, technology can also enhance these students' educational experience. Students can listen to guest speakers who specialize in specific topics. Some foreign language teachers like to associate their classes with native speakers. It helps to develop students' speaking skills further. To develop this type of reading, we need a laptop or a screen and a camera, and these are also part of innovations.

Kinesthetic Learning. Kinesthetic learners need to perform interactive activities to understand new concepts. They thrive while working on hands-on projects. Educational apps on tablets and smartphones can also help kinesthetic learners. In the above points we have regarded elements of these three types of students and what kind of technology they need to avoid difficulties in the learning process. Teachers can use a variety of technology tools to include all types of students in their lesson plans. Some online activities or tablet apps often use a combination of visuals, sounds, and interactive objectives that engage visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners.

Another of the new requirements for teaching foreign languages utilizing technology resources and the use of multimedia equipment is the creation of interaction in the lesson, it is usually called interactivity in methodology.

We believe that technologies play important role for young people who are exploding today and as a result of using innovative methods in foreign language learners, students' logical thinking skills will develop perfectly, their speech becomes fluent and the ability to answer quickly and correctly formed. Such methods and interesting technologies will evoke student a passion in order to get high knowledge, as a result of which, the teacher strives to prepare thoroughly for the lessons.

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